

A Human-Centric Decision Support System for Zero-Defect Manufacturing Enabled by Human-in-the-Loop Learning

Andreana Mitsiaki¹[0009-0004-3331-4919], Christina Tsita¹[0000-0002-2416-7396], Nikolaos Dimitriou¹[0000-0002-6650-7758] and Dimitrios Tzovaras¹[0000-0001-6915-6722]

¹ Information Technologies Institute
Centre for Research and Technology Hellas
57001, Thessaloniki, Greece

Abstract. This paper presents a Decision Support System (DSS) for Zero Defect Manufacturing (ZDM), deployed in three factories. The DSS comprises modular components that enhance decision-making through advanced visualization for monitoring, prediction, analysis, and defect detection. Its design prioritizes usability, offering comprehensive visual analytics, easy management of connected devices, human-Artificial Intelligence (AI) interaction, and interface expandability. The DSS captures product images using RGB cameras, which are analyzed by AI algorithms to detect defects. Operators can review the detection results through a user-friendly web interface and provide feedback. The significant novelty of the system lies in its application of human-in-the-loop (HITL) Learning, where human feedback is used to retrain the AI models, progressively improving the accuracy of the defect detection, as demonstrated in real-world experiments. At the same time, operators learn from their interactions with the AI, while their empirical knowledge is complemented by real-time informed data. The system fosters a synergistic collaboration between human operators and AI, reducing defective products and inspection time. In one factory, the DSS led to 90% reduction in product inspection time, enabling operators to complete inspections faster and focus on other production tasks. End-user evaluations across the three factories showed a 93% perceived ease of use and a 90% intention to use. These results highlight the system's effectiveness in advancing digital transformation in quality control, aligning with Industry 4.0/5.0 objectives.

Keywords: defect detection, decision support, artificial intelligence, human-in-the-loop Learning

1 Introduction

“Industry 4.0” refers to the fourth industrial revolution, which integrates intelligent digital technologies into production lines and has become the main standard for the manufacturing sector's digital transformation [1]. The term “Industry 5.0” emerged later to emphasize the human-centric perspective in digital transformation [2][3]. According to

Platform Industrie 4.0, “Industry 4.0” already incorporates sustainability goals, including workforce well-being, through human-centric approaches. Like previous industrial revolutions, the fourth revolution will require considerable time to fully mature before transitioning to the next phase [3]. Although technology is advancing rapidly, it represents only one aspect of the broader digital transformation, which also involves people and processes. Meanwhile, the term “Industry 5.0” is frequently used in the literature. Regardless of which terminology is considered most appropriate, a strategic goal of the manufacturing sector is the creation of ecosystems that are human-centric, eco-friendly, and resilient, with the ability to adapt to production disruptions [1][2]. A key element in this endeavor is communication among humans, machines, and products throughout the manufacturing process [4].

AI and Internet of Things (IoT) are core technologies in industrial automation and the smart factory concept [5], playing a critical role in realizing this vision. Central to this is the integration of ZDM into quality control processes, with a focus on early defect detection and corrective action [6]. ZDM consists of four main strategies: detect, predict, prevent, and repair, used in combination to ensure quality from the outset by leveraging data to predict and prevent defects [7]. It supports “Right-First-Time” (RFT) manufacturing by minimizing resource waste and shifting from traditional off-line sample measurements to in-line data collection during production. This transition improves manufacturing efficiency, accuracy and quality, while reducing defects [8]. IoT, supported by AI and operator feedback, further enhances production yield and efficiency. DSS combines these elements, creating an integrated framework to optimize manufacturing operations [9].

The OPTIMAI DSS [10] was developed to meet the requirements of ZDM within the Industry 4.0/5.0 framework, aiming to reduce defects, enhance product quality, and minimize resource waste, while supporting human operators. The system leverages AI to predict and prevent defects before they occur, and to enable early detection of faulty products. This prevents defect propagation along the production line, reducing the waste of raw materials and energy. When a defect is detected, the system can notify the operator for manual intervention or automatically execute the necessary corrective actions. Additionally, if a defective product cannot be repaired, it can be redirected to the digital marketplace, allowing part of its value to be salvaged.

A key innovation of the DSS is the integration of the HITL Learning approach into the quality control process. In this approach, human operators provide feedback to the AI models, allowing them to retrain and improve over time. Unlike traditional active learning, where models select uncertain or informative instances for labeling, this method involves human experts actively reviewing AI predictions, validating results, and offering corrective feedback. This ensures continuous system improvement and adaptation to new data and production conditions. This synergy between human expertise and data-driven insights enhances decision-making in manufacturing. The system has been deployed and tested in three pilot production sites, tailored to the specific needs of each manufacturing line. Collected data is analyzed and visualized through interactive DSS interfaces, enabling users to engage with the system and refine its performance. DSS implementation has significantly reduced quality control time while achieving high operator acceptance, demonstrating its practical value in smart manu-

facturing. The next section presents related work, followed by the proposed DSS interfaces, deployment methodology per pilot, the HITL Learning framework, and user evaluations and experiments. The final section provides the conclusions.

2 Related Work

In Industry 4.0, the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) enables efficient interaction among heterogeneous systems through event-driven frameworks, utilizing autonomous tools for data-driven decisions. According to [11], DSSs are classified based on their focus—data, communication, documents, and knowledge. Among these, knowledge-driven DSSs utilizing technologies such as data mining and AI to support autonomous decision-making. The same study highlights a hybrid DSS developed to automate the identification and rectification of problems in industrial production. To simulate production and evaluate its effectiveness, the system integrates both knowledge-based and data-driven approaches within a dynamic scheduling framework. In a real-world semiconductor application, the DSS outperformed previous decision-making strategies, significantly improving Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

By improving IoT data processing, AI-based DSS streamline operations, facilitate predictive maintenance (PdM), and improve quality control. The work of [12] examines AI applications in production planning, energy management, and supply chain management, showing how DSS boost efficiency, reduce costs, and enhance dependability. It also highlights AI's potential for autonomous decision-making in industry and discusses implementation techniques and the challenges that may arise during deployment.

The IoT, Big Data, and Machine Learning (ML) are essential tools for intelligent production, PdM, and product quality improvement. A relevant publication [13] presents a DSS that addresses the challenge of annotating component wear data in a real industrial environment. The DSS is based on a feature extraction strategy and a ML model, integrated into a cloud architecture for data collection, analysis, and storage. The work of [14] explores an integrated DSS for achieving ZDM, combining production techniques and product design, with a focus on risk identification, prioritization, and management, reducing production time and cost, and improving decision-making efficiency.

Another research [15] proposes a dynamic scheduling tool with a DSS that utilizes ZDM strategies (detection, repair, prediction, and prevention) to minimize defects in industrial settings. The paper presented in [16] develops an extensible hybrid DSS to assist operators in decision-making regarding defective components, aiming to reduce defects at later stages without disrupting production. The system can expand to incorporate growing industrial data. The importance of the operator's role in the process is emphasized in [17], particularly in ultrasound testing, a common non-destructive method for flaw detection that relies on operator expertise. To support this, DSS have been developed to automate the process and provide valuable insights, assisting the operator in making more accurate and efficient decisions.

According to the above, DSS leverage modern technologies such as IoT, Big Data, and ML to automate processes and improve production, while incorporating ZDM strategies for detecting, predicting, and preventing defects. In the context of OPTIMAI, this approach was expanded by developing a hybrid DSS that integrates AI sensors into the

production line to collect real-time data and support operators in making decisions about defective products. Additionally, HITL Learning is employed, allowing operators to participate in training the AI model, fostering collaboration between humans and machines for optimal performance.

3 Decision Support System Interfaces

The OPTIMAI DSS consists of six modules, each with its respective interface: Monitoring, Prediction, Analysis, Defect detection, Event-Notifications, and Administration.

The “Monitoring” module provides real-time visualizations of production status, including outputs from the prediction and defect detection from AI models. These insights are displayed through interactive dashboards, enabling operators to make timely decisions and take preventive actions. Data from sensors, cameras, and edge devices are continuously aggregated and processed, offering up-to-date information that enhances responsiveness and reduces downtime.

The “Prediction” module has been developed for lift manufacturing to improve the calibration process of the lift’s power unit, and specifically the valve block that controls the vertical movement of the lift (Fig. 1). It uses a neural action-prediction model to simulate the weights’ motion based on the desired velocity, allowing qualitative evaluation. A virtual environment with generative AI converts 1D velocity sequences into 2D synthetic frames, enabling operators to visualize the anticipated motion of the weights before implementing adjustments, thus reducing trial-and-error iterations [18].

Fig. 1. Prediction simulates lift movement with synthetic frames and video.

The “Analysis” module refers to historical data to support long-term decision-making. It allows users to review the outcomes of the AI modules and the data collected during the selected timeframe to identify patterns and hypothesize potential causes of defects

or suboptimal operations. Depending on the pilot, this module includes graphs for defect detection, yield and the learning curve of AI defect detection models (explained in section 5).

The “Defect Detection” module refers to the quality control interface that displays the output of the AI-based defect detection solutions in real time (Fig. 2). Each inspected product is analyzed by the underlying computer vision model, with results immediately visualized on the DSS interface. The system highlights detected anomalies, allowing operators to validate findings and, if necessary, initiate corrective actions or provide feedback to refine the detection models (details in sections 4, 5).

Fig. 2. Defect detection (a) in antenna and (b) PCB production lines

The purpose of the “Events-Notifications” module is to notify users of real-time events, such as system faults or defect discoveries, enabling swift responses and problem resolution. All notifications are stored, providing a historical record of events generated by external modules (e.g., defect detection, digital marketplace). This event history supports better decision-making for long-term process optimization.

The “Administration” interface manages DSS entities, including sensors, actuators, inspected products, monitored processes, and defect detection activities. The Blockchain module stores administrative actions executed by the users to ensure the immutability of critical data. These essential datasets are stored within Smart Contracts on distinct Private Ethereum networks, developed specifically for each pilot [19][20].

4 Methodology

4.1 Pilots Brief Description

In antenna manufacturing, the applied solution enables automated defect detection in robotic cells, synchronized with the robots’ operation in mass production. This advancement allows real-time inspection and classification of the produced antennas, enabling operators to immediately identify defects, rather than relying on later manual checks that may miss the cause of the defect [19].

In PCB manufacturing, the system significantly improves quality control through AI. At the quality control workstation, the operator initiates the process, replacing the traditional microscope with the DSS interfaces. This reduces inspection time by approximately 20 minutes (depending on the PCB model), bringing it down to about 2 minutes (a 90% reduction), including the time needed for the operator to evaluate the AI results [21].

The lift manufacturing pilot focuses on quality control of the lift power unit and its hydraulic valve block, which controls the upward and downward movement of the produced lift. The operator monitors the valve block's performance in real-time through the DSS interface, enabling quick identification of suboptimal performance and on-site adjustments using a tablet. This reduces calibration time, as the operator no longer needs to repeatedly move between the site and the side office PC to observe the measurement graphs and calibrate the valves [18].

4.2 Methodology implemented for each of the pilots

As presented in Fig. 3, various sensors and actuators were installed along the three production lines to collect real-time data. The DSS visualizes this data either by executing Python-based HTTP requests to a Middleware layer or through MQTT protocols. In the vision-based measurement systems, image outputs are analysed by AI models to detect defects. The results are sent to the Middleware and/or trigger automated actions in the production line. The DSS receives the data from Middleware and visualizes it across the various aforementioned modules (section 3) according to each pilot's requirements. It supports the visualization of multiple defect detection processes results, which may derive from the analysis of the same captured image by different AI models. The DSS incorporates an HITL Learning approach (section 5), allowing users to provide their feedback and to retrain the AI models. This feedback is transmitted back to the Middleware, into a separate entity.

Fig. 3. The overall OPTIMAI Methodology for instrumentation and visualization of the data collected and analyzed by AI in various factories

In antenna manufacturing, the defect detection process is fully automated. A PLC device controls the robotic arm, which positions an antenna onto the hydraulic press for inspection every few seconds [19]. Upon grabbing an antenna, the PLC sends a 5V

external trigger to the RGB camera, signaling it to capture an image. This image is then processed by an AI-driven defect detection system utilizing three AI models, each employing different algorithms. Each model's output is sent to a distinct Middleware entity. Finally, the PLC of the next robotic arm receives a signal indicating a defective antenna, prompting the robotic arm to place it in a separate rack. This process has significantly optimised the production line, compared to the previous practice, where antennas were stacked together and quality inspection occurred asynchronously.

In the second pilot, PCB manufacturing, the operator initiates PCB inspection by placing the board under the camera and pressing the appropriate button in the DSS interface. The camera captures a high-resolution image of the PCB, which is then analyzed by the defect detection AI models. As in the previous factory, the results are depicted in the DSS interfaces, mainly in the "Defect Detection" interface, including the captured image with overlaid defect indicators. Various industrial processes that generate defects are examined, with different AI models employed for the inspection. This paper focuses on glue/epoxy dispensing and glue dispensing calibration processes.

In the glue/epoxy dispensing processes, the AI model calculates the volume of the dispensed glue on the PCB substrate and categorizes it as normal, insufficient or excessive, using colour-coded indicators [21]. The operator inspects the results and provides feedback (details in section 5). Defective PCBs may also be sent to the marketplace to recover residual scrap value. Moreover, depending on the PCB type, the DSS may recommend adjustments to the dispenser pressure, which the operator reviews and decides whether to implement.

In the "Monitoring" tab for lift manufacturing, workers test the hydraulic valve block, which controls elevator movement. During testing, they monitor its performance in real-time, checking the valve block's velocity, sound, pressure, and vibration during both directions of lift movements. If the measurements fall outside the specified range, workers make necessary adjustments to comply with quality control standards [18].

5 Human-in-the-Loop Learning

The DSS displays quality inspection results in the defect detection interface by retrieving the image and visualising inspection results, stored in JSON format, including ground truth annotations as coloured polygons overlaid on the captured image (Fig. 4.). If users inspect the results and notice a false detection, missed defect, or misclassified defect type, they can provide feedback to the AI model by switching to annotation mode (Fig. 5.). In this mode, users can refine detection results by selecting a specific area and provide textual feedback. Upon saving, the newly annotated area is marked in pink.

The interface also includes retraining settings, allowing manual initiation or automatic triggering once a defined annotation threshold is reached, requiring no further user input.

Fig. 4. The Human-in-the-Loop Learning flow chart

Fig. 5. (a) The colour coded defects overlaid on the PCB captured image and (b) the annotation mode.

Every time an annotation is created, a new JSON file is generated for the HITL Learning module. During a retraining session, these JSON files are batched and uploaded to the appropriate Middleware entity. The AI model then uses this data as input for re-training. Once retraining is complete, the updated model can be deployed for defect detection, allowing accuracy improvement as more annotated data is collected. Details of retraining sessions, such as the number of annotations, timestamps, and model performance, are visualized in the HITL Learning graph within the DSS Analysis interface, showcasing the model's learning curve over time (Fig. 6). This approach ensures that the user actively participates in improving the model, rather than passively relying on AI algorithms alone.

Fig. 6. HITL Learning graph in the Analysis interface

Based on process requirements, classification and regression models were applied. In the antenna pilot, a YOLOv8-based object detection model [22] was trained using the ADAM optimizer with the default learning rate of 0.001, utilizing pre-trained MS COCO [23] weights to reduce training time. The dataset was split into a 90% training set and a 10% validation set, retraining the model from the initial stage of the process. Evaluation was based on accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. Training ran for up to 300 epochs, with early stopping triggered if no improvement was observed on the validation set over 50 consecutive epochs, to avoid overfitting and reduce computation time. In the PCB pilot, deep learning-based methods were employed for detecting conductive glue defects. Specifically, instance segmentation (Mask R-CNN) was used to locate glue deposits, followed by a residual neural network (R2esNet) for volume regression from RGB images [21]. To evaluate the regression models, Mean Squared Error (MSE) was employed as the evaluation metric, with a 10-fold cross-validation retraining process. This iterative approach leverages real-time data and user annotations, leading to significant MSE reduction across phases.

HITL Learning modules integrated into defect detection systems enhance the accuracy of inspection models by incorporating user feedback. Experimental results indicate that model accuracy increases with the integration of annotated defective samples into the training set. The most substantial improvements are observed in the early stages of HITL, where data scarcity significantly impacts performance. As the training set grows, the model continues to improve, suggesting that initial limitations stemmed from insufficient data rather than algorithmic shortcomings.

6 User Testing

6.1 Methodology

Designers and developers of the DSS maintained continuous communication with end-users through questionnaires and workshops, utilizing wireframes and mockups to gather feedback for iterative design, following an agile process to integrate new features based on this feedback. Combined with intermediate user testing, this process helped moderators to better understand operators' workflows and refine the system. The final

user assessment, conducted across the pilot sites, evaluated an end-to-end HITL production scenario, focusing on DSS interfaces. Participants were introduced to the system via a demonstration of the production line instrumentation, camera setup, data flow, and results visualization. Each participant tested the DSS and completed a background information and user experience questionnaire (BIQ, UXQ). The BIQ gathered demographics, job-related details, and prior experience with computer applications.

In PCB and antenna manufacturing, the first UXQ section assessed the usefulness of the different DSS modules [24]. The second section, based on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) – TAM2 [25], evaluated job relevance and the perceived usefulness for daily work. The third section used the System Usability Scale (SUS) [26]. The fourth section focused on the defect detection module, with participants rating how easy it was to (a) understand detection results, (b) use inspection tools, and (c) provide feedback via annotation mode. Participants also assessed their trust in the system’s results (with and without their feedback) [27] and their intention to use the system [25]. All questions used 5-point Likert scale from 1-5 (1: strongly disagree, 5: strongly agree). Overall satisfaction was measured with the Net Promoter Score (NPS) [28][29]. Open-ended questions at the end gathered comments based on likes and dislikes. For lift manufacturing, the UXQ included TAM- derived items on perceived usefulness, intention to use, quality and ease of understanding the results. An additional item rated UI aesthetics, along with SUS, NPS and open-ended questions.

6.2 Results

Ten operators participated in each pilot study. In the PCB and lift pilots, two participants were women, while in the antenna, one participant was a woman. In the lift pilot, most participants (7) were aged 35-44, with 90% having more than 5 years of experience. In the PCB and antenna pilots, participants’ ages ranged from 18–55 and 18–64, respectively. In the PCB pilot, 40% of users were aged 25-34, while in the antenna pilot, 40% were aged 35–44. PCB participants were evenly distributed across experience ranges (<5 years: 4, 5–10 years: 3, >10 years: 3), while 70% of antenna users had over 10 years of experience. Participants' expertise was related to quality control operations and optimization, either in practical roles or at the management level. Regarding job relevance, in the antenna pilot, 30% of users were neutral, and the rest were positive (30% agree, 40% strongly agree) (Table 1). In the PCB pilot, 40% of participants found relevant and 60% very relevant.

In the lift pilot, 80% of users were positive about system’s usefulness in their work, while 20% were neutral. In the antenna line, positivity was higher, with 10% neutral. In the PCB line, all participants were positive (30% agree, 70% strongly agree). Regarding performance improvement, nearly all lift line users were positive, with 10% disagreeing. In the antenna line, 20% were neutral, 50% agreed, and 30% strongly agreed. In the PCB line, 20% were neutral, 30% agreed, and 50% strongly agreed.

The intention to use the system was higher in antenna and PCB pilots. In the lift pilot, one user disagreed, another was neutral, and the rest were evenly split between agreeing and strongly agreeing (40% each). In the antenna line, all users intended to use the system (60% agree, 40% strongly agree), while in the PCB line 10% were neutral, 30% agreed, and 60% strongly agreed. For ease of use, both the lift and PCB lines had one neutral response, with 30% agreeing and 60% strongly agreeing. In the antenna line, 40% agreed, and 60% strongly agreed. Regarding learnability, 10% of lift line

users were neutral, 40% agreed and 50% strongly agreed. In the other two lines, all users were positive: 40% agreed and 60% strongly agreed in the antenna line, while PCB, responses were evenly split.

In the lift line, both the quality of the output and the ease of understanding were rated positively (quality: 10% neutral, 40% agree, 50% strongly agree, understanding: 10% neutral, 30% agree, 60% strongly agree). In the antenna line, users found the results easy to understand (40% agree, 60% strongly agree), and the inspection tools easy to use (30% agree, 70% strongly agree), but found the annotation mode slightly more difficult to use (20% neutral, 10% agree, 70% strongly agree). In the PCB line, the results were also easy to understand (10% neutral, 30% agree, 60% strongly agree). Users rated the inspection tools as easy to use (10% neutral, 20% agree, 70% strongly agree), and found it easy to correct false results (30% agree, 70% strongly agree). In both the antenna and PB lines, users expressed greater trust in the system's results when considering their ability to provide their feedback, with positive ratings ranging from 80% to 100% in the antenna line and from 70% to 100% in the PCB line. The NPS score was marginally favorable for the lift line at 20% (promoters 40% - detractors 20%), marginally excellent for the antenna line at 50% (promoters 60% - detractors 10%), and excellent for the PCB pilot at 60% (promoters 60% - detractors 0%).

Table 1. Indicative UXQ results

Parameter	Item	Positive rates (%)		
		<i>Lift</i>	<i>Antenna</i>	<i>PCB</i>
Relevance (TAM)	In my work, usage of the system is relevant.	-	70	100
System's Usefulness (TAM)	I think that the system would be useful at my work.	80	90	100
	I think that using the system would improve my performance in my work.	90	80	80
Intention to use (TAM)	Assuming I have access to the system, I intend to use it.	80	100	90
Ease of use (SUS)	I thought the system was easy to use.	90	100	90
Learnability (SUS)	I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly.	90	100	100
Output of the system (TAM)	The overall output of the system is of high quality.	90	-	-
	It was easy to understand the output of the system.	90	-	-
Defect detection with AL related				
Ease of defect detection (task-related)	It was easy to understand the defect detection results.	-	100	90
	It was easy to use the inspection tools (checkboxes, opacity slider, zoom in/out and pan).	-	100	90

Parameter	Item	Positive rates (%)		
		<i>Lift</i>	<i>Antenna</i>	<i>PCB</i>
Trust (inspired by 27)	It was easy to correct any false results.	-	80	100
	I feel I can trust the results of the system.	-	80	70
	I feel I can trust the results of the system as long as I provide my feedback.	-	100	100
	“How likely is it that you would recommend OPTIMAI system to a college?” - NPS score	20	50	60

In the antenna line, the system’s strengths identified in the open-ended question were in defect detection, analysis and usability. Indicatively, users appreciated its visual appeal, the way defects are displayed, and its ease of use. They also noted that the system “included the feedback from the previous evaluation everything that we asked is integrated.” Weaknesses were related to the defect detection, as well as general comments and suggestions for possible extensions. Indicatively, users recommended making the annotation mode switch more visible, enhancing the prominence of overall results, and adding options in the administration and monitoring modules. In the PCB line, users highlighted the system’s accurate defect detection compared to the current method, its colour-coded visualizations, inspection options, and the clear interface. Suggestions included improving navigation and increasing the size of the captured image area. In the lift line, positive comments focused on the depicted graphs, especially the normal ranges and the reference curves, and on having “all the data in a timely manner”. Negative comments included the small graphs size and a suggestion to allow users to modify the reference curves independently.

7 Conclusions

The proposed DSS includes modules for Monitoring, Prediction, Analysis, Event-Notifications, Administration, and Defect detection for ZDM. Its interfaces assist operators by providing real-time monitoring of production and defect occurrences. Integrated HITL Learning methods enable operators to provide annotations and actively participate in AI model retraining, improving AI results accuracy. User testing results highlighted the ease of use, higher acceptance when operators provide feedback, and strong intentions to use and recommend the system. Users' appreciation for the system’s responsiveness to their feedback during the design phase, where their suggestions were incorporated after testing, validated the project's commitment to agile development. Operators’ acceptance and reduced inspection times demonstrate the system’s alignment with Industry 4.0/5.0 and ZDM goals, effectively leveraging AI to improve production efficiency and workforce satisfaction. However, some limitations were noted. Sample sizes were small, with no more than 10 participants per pilot site, as it was not feasible to involve more operators due to the limited number of workers performing relevant roles in the factories. Regarding the interface, graph size issues must be addressed to better support lift operators using tablet devices, while the low NPS indicates a need to further explore and resolve any user concerns in the lift pilot.

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